

A STUDY ON CONSUMER PREFERENCE AND AWARENESS TOWARDS NAVARA RICE WITH REFERENCE TO KILAKARAI

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ABSTRACT

This study explores consumer preference and awareness of Navara rice in Kilakarai, known for its traditional farming methods. Navara rice, valued for its medicinal and cultural significance, is gaining attention for its health benefits. Using mixed methods, the research aims to grasp consumer perceptions, preferences, and awareness levels. Data from surveys and observations will analyze factors like taste, nutrition, health benefits, cultural importance, and pricing. The study will also evaluate the impact of marketing strategies on consumer behavior. Findings will offer insights for farmers, policymakers, and marketers to promote Navara rice sustainably, preserving traditional practices and encouraging healthier food choices.

This project focuses on understanding consumer preferences and awareness towards Navara rice, a premium variety known for its nutritional benefits and unique heritage. The study aims to gain insights into the factors influencing consumers' decision-making process when considering Navara rice, especially with its higher price point compared to other rice varieties. Through survey research and data analysis, the project examines consumer perceptions, knowledge, and attitudes towards Navara rice, as well as their willingness to pay for this specialty grain. The findings provide valuable information for producers, marketers, and policymakers to better promote and position Navara rice in the market, thereby supporting sustainable farming practices and preserving cultural heritage associated with this ancient grain.

Key Words: Consumer Awareness, Preference, Navara Rice, Traditional Crops, Market Behavior

1.1 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Navara rice, valued for its health benefits and cultural heritage, faces limited consumer acceptance despite its growing recognition. This study examines factors influencing consumer satisfaction focusing on quality perception, availability, and awareness to identify challenges and opportunities for promoting its wider consumption.

Limited Awareness: Many consumers lack knowledge of Navara rice's nutritional and cultural value, restricting informed choices and market growth.

High Cost: Limited cultivation, high production costs, and niche demand contribute to its premium pricing, affecting affordability.

Limited Availability: Restricted supply and poor distribution make Navara rice difficult to access, further driving up prices and reducing consumer reach.

1.2 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To identify the consumer awareness and perception towards Navara rice.
- To find out the positive and negative factors influencing consumers while purchasing Navara rice.
- To analyze the average amount spent by the customers for the purchase of Navara rice.
- To promote awareness about Navara rice by highlighting its nutritional benefits and heritage.
- To find out the changes that can be made in the future based on consumers preference.

1.3 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The degree of knowledge on the advantages of Navara rice is covered in this study to investigate whether the consumers prefer Navara rice over other therapeutic rice. The study looks at the variables that affect a customers decision to purchase Navara rice. To investigate how customers feel about the cost of Navara rice. The scope of this research encompasses the location of Kilakarai for study.

1.4 AREA OF THE STUDY

The study duration covers a period of 5 months from December 2023 to April 2024. Data relating to five months have been collected from the respondents from various parts of Kilakarai.

1.5 METHODOLOGY

The methodology is an essential aspect of any research of investigation. It enables the investigator to look at the problem in a systematic, meaningful and in an orderly way. The methodology comprises sources of data analyzing the data. The study is based on both primary and secondary data. The primary data has been collected from various parts of Kilakarai in Ramanathapuram district and the secondary data has been collected from journals and through internet.

1.6 SAMPLING DESIGN

The research is carried out in the form of survey which is done in east, west, south, north streets of Kilakarai in Ramanathapuram district. The target population for our study is household and working persons. The sample will be selected by simple random sampling.

1.7 REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Debdulal Bhattacharjee, Sabita Nauri (2015) researched on "Heavy metals in Navara rice (*oryza sativa*)". This study reported the differential levels of accumulation of 12 heavy metals, including Cu, Fe, Mn, Zn and Ag, in decorated grains of 130 rice landraces. The study also reported the extraordinary up take and bio accumulation of metallic silver by a rare rice and-race, Garib-sal. Most of the landraces examined here, including Garib-sal, have disappeared from rice farms,¹⁷ as a result of farmers' preference for improved varieties.

Richard (2017) conducted a study on "Preference of customer". In his study he concluded that, the customer has his or her own life experiences, which will cause variable characteristics and variable preferences in purchasing. It is different to summarize in an easy word, and it is an important thing for a company to make enough research to collect data before they produce products. Once a company confirms its target customers, then make customer preferences research is inevitable.

Jayarajan.k, Dhanya punnoli(2023) conducted a study on "Resilience to natural hazards among the Njavara Rice farming communities in Kerala". In their study they concluded that, farming communities are constantly at risk of weather and climate aberrations. Navara is an indigenous rice variety that is famous for its medicinal and nutritional properties. In this case study, multivariate statistical techniques were used to evaluate spatial and temporal variations in sampling sites

1.8 INCOME WISE CLASSIFICATION OF THE RESPONDENTS**TABLE 1****INCOME OF THE RESPONDENTS**

S.NO	INCOME	NO OF RESPONDENTS	% OF THE RESPONDENTS
1	Less than RS2,000	0	0
2	Rs 2,001-Rs 5,000	4	8
3	Rs 5,001-Rs10,000	20	40
4	Above Rs10,000	26	52
	TOTAL	50	100

Source : primary data

INTREPRETTION:

The above table reveals that 0% of the respondents income is less than Rs. 2,000, 8% of the respondents income is between Rs. 2,001- Rs. 5,000, 40% of the respondents income is between Rs. 5,001 – Rs. 10,000 and 52% of the respondents income is above Rs. 10,000.

The above table concluded that 56% of the respondents' monthly income is above Rs.10,000.

1.9 RESPONDENTS' USUAL RICE PURCHASE FOR DAILY MEAL**TABLE 2****RESPONDENTS' USUAL RICE PURCHASE FOR DAILY MEAL**

S.NO	USUAL RICE PURCHASE FOR DAILY MEAL	NO OF RESPONDENTS	% OF THE RESPONDENTS
1	White rice	46	92
2	Samba rice	0	0
3	Unpolished rice	3	6
4	other	1	2
	TOTAL	50	100

Source: primary data

INTERPRETATION:

The above table shows that 92% of the respondents usually purchase white rice, 0% of the respondents usually purchase samba rice, 6% of the respondents purchase unpolished rice and 2% of the respondents purchase other type of rice for daily meal.

The above table concludes that 92% of the respondents usually purchase white rice for their daily meal.

1.10 FREQUENCY OF RICE PURCHASE

TABLE 3
FREQUENCY OF RICE PURCHASE OF RESPONDENTS

S.NO	FREQUENCY OF PURCHASING	NO OF RESPONDENTS	% OF THE RESPONDENTS
1	Everyday	2	4
2	Once a week	12	24
3	Once a month	31	62
4	Non-periodical	5	10
	TOTAL	50	100

Source: primary data

INTERPRETATION:

The above table shows that 4% of the respondents purchase rice everyday, 24% of the respondents purchase rice once in a week, 62% of the respondents purchase rice once in a month and 10% of the respondents purchase rice non periodically.

Based on the above table, it can be concluded that 62% of the respondents purchase rice once in a month.

1.11 AVERAGE AMOUNT SPENT ON RICE PURCHASE**TABLE 4****AVERAGE AMOUNT SPENT ON RICE PURCHASE OF RESPONDENTS**

S.NO	AVERAGE AMOUNT SPENT ON RICE PURCHASE	NO OF RESPONDENTS	% OF THE RESPONDENTS
1	Below Rs.50	4	8
2	Rs.51-Rs.100	9	18
3	Rs.101-Rs.200	13	26
4	Above Rs.200	24	58
	TOTAL	50	100

Source: primary data

INTERPRETATION:

The above table shows that 8% of the respondents spent below Rs. 50, 18% of the respondents spent between Rs. 51–Rs.100, 26% of the respondents spent between Rs. 101–Rs. 200 and 58% of the respondents spent above Rs. 200 for purchasing of rice.

Based on the above table, it can be concluded that 58% of the respondents have spent more than Rs. 200 on buying rice.

1.12 FREQUENCY OF NAVARA RICE CONSUMPTION**TABLE 5****FREQUENCY OF NAVARA RICE CONSUMPTION**

S.NO	FREQUENCY OF NAVARA RICE CONSUMPTION	NO OF RESPONDENTS	% OF THE RESPONDENTS
1	Daily	0	0
2	Weekly once	5	10
3	Monthly once	19	38
4	Very rarely	26	52
	TOTAL	50	100

Source: primary data

INTERPRETATION:

The above table illustrates that 0% of the respondents are not consuming Navara rice daily, 10% of the respondent are consuming weekly once, 38% of the respondents are consuming monthly once and 52% of the respondents are consuming very rarely.

The above table concludes that 52% of the respondents are consuming very rarely.

1.13 PROBLEMS FACED WHILE PURCHASING NAVARA RICE**TABLE 6****PROBLEMS FACED WHILE PURCHASING NAVARA BY RESPONDENTS**

S.NO	PROBLEMS FACED WHILE PURCHASING NAVARA RICE	NO OF RESPONDENTS	% OF THE RESPONDENTS
1	High price	32	64
2	Non-availability	13	26
3	Low quality	0	0
4	Never purchased	5	10
	TOTAL	50	100

Source: primary data

INTERPRETATION:

Table indicates that 64% of respondents are concerned about high price, while 26% are concerned about non-availability. 0% of the respondents are concerned about low quality, and the rest being 10% have never made a purchase.

The above table concludes that 64% of the respondents have issues with high prices while making purchases of Navara rice.

1.14 OPINION ABOUT NAVARA RICE PRICING**TABLE 7****OPINION ON NAVARA RICE PRICING OF RESPONDENTS**

S.NO	OPINION ON PRICING OF NAVARA RICE	NO OF RESPONDENTS	% OF THE RESPONDENTS
1	Cheap	0	0
2	Reasonable	4	8
3	Expensive	15	30
4	Very expensive	31	62
	TOTAL	50	100

Source: primary data

INTERPRETATION:

The above table illustrates that 0% of the respondents' opinions about the prices of Navara rice is cheap, 8% of the respondents' opinion is reasonable, 30% of the respondents' opinion is expensive and 62% of the respondents' opinion is very expensive.

Based on the above table it concluded that 62% of the respondents' opinion on Navara rice pricing is very expensive.

1.15 LACK OF AWARENESS ABOUT NAVARA RICE**TABLE 8****LACK OF AWARENESS ABOUT NAVARA RICE BY RESPONDENTS**

S.NO	LACK OF AWARENESS ABOUT NAVARA RICE	NO OF RESPONDENTS	% OF THE RESPONDENTS
1	Strongly Agree	32	64
2	Agree	15	30
3	Disagree	2	4
4	Strongly disagree	1	2
	TOTAL	50	100

Source: primary data

INTERPRETATION:

The above table 4.2.23 shows that 64% of the respondents strongly agree that there is not enough awareness about Navara rice, 30% of the respondents agree that there is lack of awareness, 4% of the respondents disagree that, there is lack of awareness about Navara rice and 2% of the respondents strongly disagree that, there is not enough awareness about Navara rice.

Based on the above table, it can be concluded that 72% of the respondents are strongly agree that there is insufficient awareness about Navara rice.

1.16 CORRELATION BETWEEN EDUCATION LEVEL AND REASON FOR USING NAVARA RICE BY RESPONDENTS

The co-efficient of correlation is calculated between the educational level and reason for using Navara Rice by the respondents.

a) Let us take educational level as X variable and reason for using Navara Rice as Y.

TABLE 9

X(Education)	School level	Undergraduate	Postgraduate	Illiterate	TOTAL
No of respondents	4	34	10	2	50
Y(Reason for buying Navara rice)	Past experience	Doctor's recommendation	High nutritional value	No, never consumed	TOTAL
No of respondents	23	14	8	5	50

CALCULATION OF CORRELATION

X	X²	Y	Y²	X/Y
4	16	23	529	92
34	1156	14	196	476
10	100	8	64	80
2	4	5	25	10
∑x=50	∑X²=1276	∑y=50	∑y²=814	∑xy=658

$$R = \frac{n(\sum xy) - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{[n(\sum X^2) - (\sum x)^2][n(\sum y^2) - (\sum y)^2]}$$

$$R = \frac{4(658) - (50)(50)}{[4(1276) - (50)^2][4(814) - (50)^2]}$$

$$= \frac{2632 - 2500}{[5104 - 2500][3256 - 2500]}$$

$$= \frac{132}{5104 - 2500 \times 3256 - 2500}$$

$$= \frac{132}{\sqrt{2604} \times \sqrt{756}}$$

$$= \frac{132}{51.02 \times 27.49}$$

$$= 0.094$$

$$= 0.094$$

$$= 0.094$$

$$= 0.094$$

INTERPRETATION:

The relationship between education and reason of buying Navara rice are positively correlated with the magnitude of **0.094**

1.17 CHI-SQUARE TEST

Chi-square is a statistical test commonly used to compare observed data with data we would expect to obtain according to a specific hypothesis. Chi –square tests are often constructed from a sum of squared errors, or through the sample variance. Test statistics that follow a chi-squared distribution arise from an assumption of independent, normally distributed data, which is in many cases due to the central limit theorem.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN OCCUPATION AND USAGE OF NAVARA RICE BY RESPONDENTS

TABLE 10

Usage/Income	Student	Employee	Non-employee	Others	Total
Daily	0	0	0	0	0
Weekly once	0	1	3	1	5
Monthly once	0	1	10	8	19
Very rarely	0	1	6	19	26
Total	0	3	19	28	50

$E1 = \frac{0 \cdot 0}{0.50}$	$E5 = \frac{5 \cdot 0}{0.50}$	$E9 = \frac{19 \cdot 0}{0.50}$	$E13 = \frac{26 \cdot 0}{0.50}$
$E2 = \frac{0 \cdot 3}{0.50}$	$E6 = \frac{5 \cdot 3}{0.50} = 0.3$	$E10 = \frac{19 \cdot 3}{0.50} = 1.14$	$E14 = \frac{26 \cdot 3}{0.50} = 1.56$
$E3 = \frac{0 \cdot 19}{0.50}$	$E7 = \frac{5 \cdot 19}{0.50} = 1.9$	$E11 = \frac{19 \cdot 19}{0.50} = 7.22$	$E15 = \frac{26 \cdot 19}{0.50} = 9.88$
$E4 = \frac{0 \cdot 28}{0.50}$	$E8 = \frac{5 \cdot 28}{0.50} = 2.8$	$E12 = \frac{19 \cdot 28}{0.50} = 10.64$	$E16 = \frac{26 \cdot 28}{0.50} = 14.56$

THE TABLE OF EXPECTED FREQUENCY

0	0	0	0	0
0	0.3	1.9	2.8	5
0	1.14	7.22	10.64	19
0	1.56	9.98	14.56	26.1

CALCULATION OF CHI-SQUARE

O	E	(O-E)	(O-E)²	(O-E)²/E
0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0
1	0.3	0.7	0.49	1.64
1	1.14	-0.14	0.0196	0.017
1	1.56	-0.56	0.3136	0.20
0	0	0	0	0
3	1.19	1.81	3.2761	2.75
10	7.22	2.78	7.7284	1.07
6	9.98	-3.98	15.8404	1.58
0	0	0	0	0
1	2.8	-1.8	3.24	1.15
18	10.64	7.36	54.1696	5.09
19	14.56	4.44	19.7136	1.35
			Total	14.847

$$\text{DOF}=(4-1)(4-1)$$

$$=(3)(3)$$

$$\text{For } V=9X^2(0.05)=16.919$$

INTERPRETATION:

The calculated value of chi-square 14.847 is less than the table value 16.919. Therefore, hypothesis is accepted. Hence, it can be concluded that there is no significant relationship between occupation and usage of Navara rice

1.17 LACK OF AWARENESS TOWARDS NAVARA RICE**TABLE 11**

S.N O	Opinion	Weight	No of respondents	Weighted score
1	Strongly agree	4	32	128
2	Agree	3	15	45
3	Disagree	2	2	4
4	Strongly disagree	1	1	1
	TOTAL	10	50	178

Source: Primary data

Opinion score percentage=178/200*100=89**INTERPRETATION:**

As indicated by the weighted score of 178, reflecting a moderate level of the opinion among respondents, 89% of respondents strongly concurred that there is insufficient awareness regarding Navara rice.

1.18 CONSUMERS' OPINION TOWARDS NAVARA RICE PRICING**TABLE 12**

S.NO	Opinion	Weight	No of respondents	Weighted score
1	Very expensive	4	31	124
2	Expensive	3	15	45
3	Reasonable	2	4	8
4	Cheap	1	0	0
	TOTAL	10	50	177

Source: Primary data

Opinion score percentage=177/200*100=88.5**INTERPRETATION:**

According to the weighted score of 177, which indicates that respondents have a moderate view regarding the price of Navara rice, 88.5% of respondents agreed that the Navara rice is very expensive.

1.19 FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- Majority of the respondents are between the age group of 31 – 40 years, 38% comes under this age group.
- As per the survey, the educational qualification of the respondents, shows that 8% of the respondents are school level, 64% of the respondents are undergraduate, 20% of the respondents are postgraduate and 4% of the respondents are illiterate. The majority of the respondents are undergraduate.
- As per the survey, most of the respondent's family size is in between 3-5 members which is 52%.
- Out of 50 respondents, 4% of the respondents are student, 56% of the respondents are employee, 38% of the respondents are non - employee and 1% of the respondents are from others.
- The survey states that majority of the respondents income is above Rs.10,000, which is 56%.
- Based on the survey, the majority 92% of the respondents usually purchase white rice for their daily meal.
- It is found that 62% of the respondents purchase rice once in month.
- Majority of the respondents purchase rice between 11–15kg, 60% of the respondents comes under this category.
- As per the survey respondents spend amount on purchasing rice, shows that that 8% of the respondents spend below Rs.50, 18% of the respondents spend between Rs.51–Rs. 100, 26% of the respondents spend between Rs. 101 – Rs. 200 and 58% of the respondents spend above Rs.200 for purchasing of rice. The majority of the respondents spend above Rs. 200 for purchasing rice.
- The survey find out that 90% of the respondents are customer of Navara rice, 10% of the

respondents are not a customer of Navara rice.

- Out of 50, the majority 48% of the respondents using Black color glumed color of Navara rice.
- As per the survey, the majority of the respondents of 44% got information through internet about Navara rice.
- Based on the survey it reveals, that 52% of the respondents out of 100%, are consuming Navara rice very rarely.
- It is found that, 54% of respondents said that Navara rice helped in maintaining diabetes.
- Majority of the respondents are using Navara rice based on their past experience, which is 46%.
- Out of 50, 58% of the respondents, prefer to purchase Navara rice through online.
- As per the survey of availability of Navara rice in their local area, it shows that 10% of the respondents selected not readily available, 8% of the respondents selected that Navara rice is available occasionally, 28% of the respondents selected that Navara rice is difficult to find and 54% of the respondents indicated they always prefer to purchase online. Majority of respondents prefer to purchase through online.
- The survey find out that 64% of the respondents have issues with high prices while making purchase of Navara rice.
- Based on the survey, the majority 72% of the respondents opinion on Navara rice pricing is very expensive.
- According to the survey it reveals, that 84% of the respondents are loyal customer of Navara rice, 16% of the respondents wants to experimenting other types of rice variety.
- The survey shows the respondents awareness about Navara rice. 54% of the respondents level of awareness is very high, 24% of the respondents awareness is high, 12% of the respondents awareness is low and 10% of the respondents awareness is very low.
- The majority 72% of the respondents are strongly agree that there is insufficient awareness about Navara rice.

- As per the survey of factor which make people hesitate to purchase Navara rice shows that, 16% of the respondents agree that people hesitate to buy Navara rice due to high price, 84% of the respondents strongly agree that people hesitate to buy Navara rice due to high price and none of the respondents disagree or strongly disagree that people hesitate to purchase Navara rice due to its high price.
- As a result of the weighted score of 184, which indicates the respondent's opinion towards Navara rice high price is high and 92% of respondents strongly agreed that the high price makes people hesitate to purchase Navara rice.
- The weighted score of 178, which denotes moderate opinion among respondents on the level of awareness regarding Navara rice is, moderate.
- According to the weighted score of 177, which indicates that respondents have a moderate view regarding the price of Navara rice, 88.5% of respondents agreed that the Navara rice is very expensive.
- The relationship between education and reason of buying Navara rice are positively correlated with the magnitude of 0.094.

1.20 SUGGESTIONS

Some of the suggestions that can be derived from the conducted study are:

- Navara rice industries can make arrangement for individual retail shops for their products.
- Price is the most important factor to determine the preference of consumers.
- Retailers can reduce the price of the product.
- Navara rice industries and government can organize awareness campaigns on Navara rice.
- Retailers can conduct additional promotional activities, as there is insufficient advertisement for Navara rice
- Offer customers sample packs of Navara rice so that they can experience it.
- To attract customers and set out on shop shelves, think about utilizing eco-friendly materials, bright colors, and informational labels about Navara rice.
- Identifying the target market, understanding consumer trends and preferences, and comparing competition are all achieved through market research.
- Increase awareness and boost sales at retail locations by providing affordable prices, special promotions, and product displays.
- Providing a book of health benefits of Navara rice to consumers so they can learn more further about it.
- Making affordable to every class of peoples in the society.

1.21 CONCLUSION

The study on consumer preference and awareness towards Navara rice has shed light on the growing interest and appreciation for this traditional variety of rice. Despite its higher cost compared to other types of rice, Navara rice offers numerous health benefits, exceptional quality, and a rich cultural heritage. It is important to take measures to make it affordable to all class of people in society. Through surveys, interviews, and analysis, it has become evident that consumers are increasingly recognizing the unique qualities and benefits of Navara rice, such as its nutritional value, health benefits, and cultural significance.

The study also highlights the need for enhanced awareness and education initiatives to further promote the benefits of Navara rice and encourage its adoption among a wider audience.

Consumer preference is very important in order to increase the profitability and customer base. This research study was conducted to increase our current understanding level of Navara rice to analyze consumers decision making in particular, if the above suggestions are implemented, the Navara rice industry will research a higher target in the near future.

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